

**Kinetics of electrochemical properties of soils under submerged conditions (average of two replications).
India**

Soil no.	21 Mar	23 Mar	27 Mar	30 Mar	31 Apr	1 Apr	3 Apr	8 Apr	14 Apr	22 Apr	28 Jun
<i>Kinetics of pH of soil</i>											
Soil-1	4.9	5.3	6.3	6.7	6.8	6.7	6.7	6.9	6.9	7.0	6.9
Soil-2	5.0	5.4	6.5	6.7	6.9	6.7	6.7	6.9	6.8	6.8	7.0
Soil-3	4.3	5.0	6.1	6.5	6.8	6.6	6.6	6.9	6.8	6.0	6.1
Soil-4	4.5	4.8	5.3	5.7	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.8	6.8	6.9	7.0
<i>Kinetics of Ec (mmho/cm) of supernatant liquid</i>											
Soil-1	< 0.05	0.05	0.12	0.18	0.38	0.39	0.41	0.20	0.05	0.05	0.05
Soil-2	< 0.05	0.05	0.05	0.14	0.17	0.19	0.18	0.15	0.05	0.05	0.05
Soil-3	< 0.05	0.05	0.15	0.31	0.42	0.51	0.50	0.22	0.05	0.05	0.05
Soil-4	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.13	0.26	0.28	0.32	0.11	0.15	0.05
<i>Kinetics of Eh (mV) of soil</i>											
Soil-1	+160	+115	+15	-130	-130	-173	-175	-178	-168	-158	-135
Soil-2	+178	+120	+20	-110	-135	-150	-180	-163	-160	-145	-130
Soil-3	+205	+ 85	+ 8	-135	-148	-160	-185	-180	-188	-168	-150
Soil-4	+205	+145	+43	+15	-33	- 60	-123	-175	-180	-155	-130

Appraisal of available phosphorus in alluvial soils for rice

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An ideal soil test will satisfactorily predict nutrient availability from the soil and, thus, the potential crop yields. The applicability of different soil test methods for estimating the available phosphorus (P) status of soils varies with soils or crops. This study was to evaluate the suitability of soil-testing methods to predict P availability to rice, and to determine the critical limit of available P for alluvial soils that have essentially alkaline reaction.

Greenhouse pot-culture experiments used 3 kg/pot of surface soil sample (0-15 cm) representing arid brown soil collected from 23 rice-growing sites in Ludhiana district. The pH of the soils tested ranged from 8.8 to 9.4; electrical conductivity, 0.10 to 0.35 mmho/cm; organic carbon, 0.02 to 0.75%; $KMnO_4N$, 11 to 84 ppm; and NH_4OAc extractable K, 23 to 24 ppm. The treatments consisted of a control (no fertilizer P) and 50 ppm P_2O_5 (as superphosphate), replicated three times. Five 20-day-old seedlings of Jaya raised in P-free and sand culture were transplanted in each pot, harvested 60

days later, and analyzed for total P. The soil samples were tested for available P with four extractants — 0.5N $NaHCO_3$, pH 8.5; Bray I and Bray II extractants; and 0.03 N NH_4F + 0.1% NaEDTA extractant.

The dry-matter yield varied from 7 to 16 g/pot in the no-P treatment and 8 to

21 g/pot in the P-treated pots, indicating that P application increased the dry matter yield from 8 to 114% (yield decreased by 3% in 2 soils). Plant P uptake varied from 11 to 28 mg/pot in the control and 12 to 38 mg/pot in P-treated pots. The increase in P uptake with P treatment from the control varied from -7 to 148%.

Correlation was highly significant ($r = 0.49^{**}$), between Olsen P of soil and total P uptake by rice, giving the regression equation: $Y = 14.64 + 0.70 x$ (where Y is total P uptake in mg/pot and x is Olsen P in ppm). Similarly, a significant correlation ($r = 0.44^*$) was found between Bray I-P in soil and total P uptake by rice. Evidently Olsen's extractant for estimating available P in these soils is more satisfactory for rice.

Rice in soils with Olsen-P below 4.5 ppm (critical level as determined by using the scatter diagram of Cates and Nelson 1965) will respond to P application (see figure). The critical level of 4.5 ppm P was also obtained when the percentage of dry-matter yield or control yield was related to Olsen-P in soils. ■

Relationship between Olsen-P in soil and percentage of phosphorus uptake by rice. Ludhiana, India.